

MEN'S AND WOMEN'S VERBAL EMOTIONAL LAYER VOICING TOOLS (ON THE EXAMPLE OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES)

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Abstract:

This article describes about men's and women's verbal emotional layer voicing tools on the example of English and Uzbek languages. Moreover, there some approaches and concepts have been analyzed.

Key words: speech, emotional layer, voicing tools, heteronormative, gender stereotypes.

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Speech is the use of language in the processes of expression and exchange of ideas, a certain way of life of language as a separate type of social activity. Speech refers to the processes of its oral (voice) and written manifestation, that is, the process of speaking and its result (speech ideas, works, stored in memory or recorded in writing). In the linguistic theory, the concept of speech is contrasted with the abstract concept of language, which is a system of means of expression accepted in a specific language community, and with the specific, somewhat more general concept of language, which is one of the most characteristic manifestations of social existence (life). Original speech (external speech) that serves to convey information and messages to other people in order to influence their behavior and activities, i.e. speaking, in the form of articulation of language signs perceived by hearing organs (recorded and repeated using sound recording equipment) or in writing, appears in the form of conditional reflection.

In addition to original speech ("external speech"), there is also internal speech. It focuses on discussing and solving various issues that help the speaker to know. Internal speech takes place on the basis of external notes, without the use of sound or writing, only in the form of auditory processes that take place with clear images of the words in the voice. Written speech differs from oral speech in that it is somewhat formed, the words are carefully selected, grammatically clear but complex, and the tone, facial expressions, and hand movements characteristic of oral speech cannot be used directly. There are monologic and dialogic types of speech. In addition to the communication-intervention function, speech can perform other functions, such as a poetic function. A special form of speech is reading. Each person's speech is individual and has its own characteristics; however, the main elements of the language - vocabulary and grammatical structure do not belong only to individuals, but are universal, that is, they apply to a specific language community in general. Speech is closely related to a person's thinking, his mind. A person's thoughts are formed and exist in speech. Thanks to the speech and on the basis of the speech, it becomes possible to abstractly reflect the existence in a general way, to think logically and conceptually, leaving the sphere of individuality and becoming a product of the community. Speech is of great importance in the manifestation and action of other aspects of a person's psyche, his

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intuition, perception, memory, thoughts, feelings, will, etc., and in the development of a person's consciousness. Depending on the field of speech application, artistic speech, scientific speech, and official speech have forms. In any form and in any case, accuracy, fluency, simplicity, impressiveness should remain the most important features of speech.

The study of the relationship between gender and emotional expression is the study of the differences between men and women in behavior that expresses emotions. These differences in emotional expression may be primarily due to cultural expectations of femininity and masculinity. Many psychologists reject the notion that men experience emotions less frequently than women do. Instead, researchers have suggested that men exhibit restrictive emotionality. Restrictive emotionality refers to a tendency to inhibit the expression of certain emotions, and an unwillingness to self-disclose intimate feelings. Men's restrictive emotionality has been shown to influence health, emotional appraisal, and overall identity. Furthermore, tendencies toward restrictive emotionality are correlated with an increased risk of certain anxiety disorders. It has been found that men and women each more accurately display gender-stereotypic expressions: men more accurately express anger, contempt, and happiness, while women more accurately express fear and happiness. Other studies have shown that women show higher levels of expression accuracy and judgement of nonverbal emotional cues than men overall. These patterns are not consistent across cultures, suggesting that socialization influences gender differences in emotional expression.

Another study suggests that people tend to exhibit more intense negative facial expressions in solitary conditions, and smile more when others are present. In this experiment, men and women did not differ in their anger expression in non-social conditions. However, women were more likely to express their anger in the solitary condition as opposed to the social condition. Men, on the other hand, seemed to be less concerned with appearing positive to others; they showed no difference in their expression of anger based on whether or not others were present. The second major argument in support of social influences on emotion expression involves the idea that a society's gender roles reinforce gender differences. Social constructionism states that children grow up in the context of gender roles that naturally place them in role-specific situations, influencing their emotion expression in that context. Gender stereotypes in heteronormative societies enforce expectations for women to suppress anger and contempt, but express other emotions using words and facial expressions; and discourage men from verbally expressing emotions, with the exception of anger or contempt. As an adaptive feature, regulation of expression of emotion involves consideration of the social demands of any given situation. Studies have shown that "fewer gender differences in emotion expression may be found when children are with someone they trust and know well than when children are with an unfamiliar person". Generally, people are trained to behave in a "socially acceptable" way around strangers or acquaintances, suggesting that the social context of an environment can shape the levels of emotion expression.

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